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08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.11 Marketing
08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
08.00.13 Menejment
08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
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MUNDARIJA

Цифровизация социально-трудовых отношений: вызовы и перспективы для работников	18
Абдумухтаров Анваржон Акрамжонович	
O'zbekistonda faoliyat ko'rsatayotgan soliq to'lovchi yuridik shaxslarning iqtisodiy faoliyatini rag'batlantirish masalalari.....	26
To'xtaboyev Nuriddin Isomiddin o'g'li	
Ecotourism in Protected Areas: A Literature Review.....	32
Ismoilova Maftuna Mamat qizi	
Iqtisodiyotning innovatsion rivojlanishi sharoitida xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirishning hududiy xususiyatlari.....	38
Primova Shaxlo Jumayevna	
Statistik baholash va ekonometrik modellashtirish orqali biznes rivojlanish tendensiyalarini samaradorligini baholash.....	43
Xabibullayev Ibrohim, Saidova Marhabo Xabibullo qizi	
Tijorat banklarida xususiy kapital hisobi va auditini takomillashtirish	52
Qodirova Zilola Maxmud qizi	
Qo'shilgan qiymat solig'i ma'muriyatchiligining ilg'or xorij tajribasi.....	57
Erkayev Nodir Xudayberdiyevich	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotni joriy etish holati va asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	71
Madraximova Zulfiya Nurmatovna, Ishankulova Komila Kurbanovna, Ortiqboeva Aziza Xolmurza qizi, Omonkulova Ro'zigul Akmaljon qizi	
Challenges and opportunities in implementing green economy indicators in uzbekistan's industrial sector under the fourth industrial revolution.....	76
Shodmonov Ruslan Golib ugli, Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarga ishchi kuchi oqimi va O'zbekiston mehnat bozoridagi o'zgarishlar.....	89
Tilabova Kumush Farhod qizi	
Mamlakatda "yashil" iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	95
Yuldashboyev Azizulloh Bunyodbek o'g'li, Matkarimov Inomjon Baxtiyorovich	
"Ta'lim muassasalarida moliyaviy resurslarni samarali rejalashtirish va boshqarish"	101
Buyetdinov M.J., Medetbayeva D.T.	
Enhancing utilization and minimization of renewable energy systems in uzbekistan	105
Toyirova Hamida Umedovna	
Tijorat banklari daromadini oshirishda aholining savodxonligi va xulq atvorining roli	114
Shakhlo Davirova	
2020–2024-yillarda o'zbekistondagi iqtisodiy o'sish dinamikasi	120
Akbarov Nodir, Ibdullayev Navro'zbek	
O'zbekistonda xalqaro moliyaviy institutlarning yashil moliyalashtirish jarayonidagi roli va strategik yo'nalishlari	125
Gulmira Axmadjonova Xabibulla qizi	
Sug'urta tizimiga raqamli texnologiyalarning ta'siri	133
Uzaqova Kamola Bexzodovna, Yahyoyev Bahriddinxon Bahroil o'g'li	
Improving payment services practices in commercial banks: strategies for efficiency and security	138
Mamayusuf Abdusamatov	
Jahon moliya tizimi: asosiy tendensiyalar va rivojlanishning innovation yo'nalishlari	143
Ataniyazov Jasurbek Xamidovich	
Повышение конкурентоспособности экологического туризма Узбекистана путём развития всесезонных горных туристических центров.....	150
Ахмедходжаев Равшан Темурович	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyatida valyuta operatsiyalarini takomillashtirish	157
Safarov Alisher Ibrohim o'g'li	

Oliy ta'lim tizimini miqdoriy va sifat ko'rsatkichlari asosida baholashning kompleks metodologiyasi.....	163
Hakimova Mushtariybonu Hamid qizi, Bozorova Muazzam Hamid qizi	
Ko'chmas mulkni boshqarish samaradorligini baholashning uslubiy yondashuvlari	167
Mirdjalilova Dildora Shuxratovna	
Xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirishda kichik biznesning ahamiyati va uning innovatsion rivojlantirishdagi muhim xususiyatlari	173
Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna	
Результаты долгосрочного прогнозирования и стратегического анализа эффективной организации современного управления жилищным фондом.....	178
Бердиева Дилфуза Ахатовна	
Improving long-term assets accounting and auditing	184
Gulboy Yusupov	
Davlat budjeti va xususiy sektor ishtirokida oliy ta'limni moliyalashtirishning optimal modeli.....	189
Bozorov Alisher Ro'zimurodovich	
Xufyona iqtisodiyotni qisqartirishda soliq islohotlari va raqamli texnologiyalar: O'zbekiston tajribasi va xalqaro yondashuvlar.....	193
Choriev Makhmayokub, Karimov Mamurbek, Xamrayev Olimjon, Urazov Mansur	
Bank aksiyalarining bozordagi narx dinamikasi va unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	200
Nomozov Samandar Shuxrat o'g'li	
Sanoatda rivojlanish kafolati: moliyaviy boshqaruvni raqamli transformatsiya orqali avtomatlashtirish.....	206
To'qliyev Abdirauf Bahodir o'g'li	
Inson kapitalini rivojlantirishning jamiyat farovonligi, aholi daromadlariga ta'siri.....	214
Bozorova Saxobat Abdujapparovna	
Анализ конкурентной среды: методология, примеры и этапы процесса.....	219
Садикова Раъно Абдуллаевна	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarning nazariy asoslari va ular bilan ishlash mexanizmining zaruriyati	225
Salixova G.J	
Iqtisodiyotda energiya xavfsizligiga erishishning xorij tajribasi.....	230
Samandarov Og'abek Alisher o'g'li	
Measuring methodologies of influence of the esg factors	235
Tolipova Feruza Alisherovna	
Совершенствование налогового администрирования в условиях экологически устойчивого развития.....	240
Омонов Отажон Журакулович	
Moliyaviy vositalar asosida erkin iqtisodiy zonalarni rivojlantirish strategiyasini takomillashtirish	249
Quziev Ravshan Ramazanovich	
Методологические аспекты внедрения управленческого учета в университетах Узбекистана.....	253
Каршиева Мохинур Олим кизи	
Budjet tashkilotlarida tovar-moddiy zaxiralar hisobini takomillashtirish (tibbiyot muassasalari misolida)	257
Tulyaganov Abdumalik Abdiraximovich	
Умные города как фактор экономического развития.....	261
Нозима Кахрамоновна Хакбердиева	
Перспективы зеленого фактора экономического роста в Республики Узбекистан.....	266
Исламова Насиба Улугбек кизи, Абдурашидов Отабек Улугбекович, Мамасалиева Мукаддас Ибадуллаевна	
Qurilish korxonalarida sifat menejmentini joriy qilish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	270
Ergashev O'tkir, Saidov Mash'al Samadovich	
Xorazm viloyatida eksportni rivojlantirish uchun potensial imkoniyatlar va ularni baholash.....	275
Fozil Xolmurotov	
Maishiy xizmatlar sohasini davlat tomonidan tartibga solishning nazariy jihatlarini.....	282
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	

O'zbekiston hududlarida chakana kreditlashning o'sishi.....	289
Eshqobulova Charos O'roq qizi	
Empowering uzbekistan's grain enterprises: innovative strategies for sustainable growth and operational efficiency.....	292
Kurbanova Dildora Abdurakhmanovna	
Kapital investitsiyalarga doir axborotlarni xususiy kapital to'g'risidagi hisobotda aks ettirish uslubiyatini takomillashtirish	298
Boronov Bobur Farxodovich, Muxammadiev Zarrux Umarovich	
To'qimachilik korxonalarining yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishi va yengil sanoat korxonalarini muqobil energiyadan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	303
Xolbekova Feruzaxon Rasulovna, Jalolova Aziza Jalol qizi	
Research on the effects of interest rate, inflation rate and gross domestic product (GDP) on the level of foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows (evidence from Uzbekistan).....	307
Azimov Shakhzod	
Organik mahsulotlar eksportini rag'batlantirishda maqsadli bozorlarga yo'naltirilgan marketing strategiyalari.....	314
Xidirov Shohrux Bobir o'g'li	
Korxonada iqtisodini barqarorligini ta'minlash masalalari.....	319
Abdullayev Maqsud Abdumaxmudovich	
Внедрение инновационных методов управления человеческих ресурсов в строительных компаниях.....	323
Джуроева Гузаль Шавкатовна	
Sug'urta zararlarini baholashda sun'iy intellektni qo'llash istiqbollari	328
Shoraximova Zilola Nasirdjonovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi mahalliy budjet tizimini moliyalashtirish masalalari	332
Qo'ldoshev Diyov O'rol o'g'li	
Raqamli texnologiyalar asosida raqamli ekotizimlar va ularning biznes-jarayonlarga ta'sirini aniqlashga ilmiy qarashlar tahlili	336
Suvanova Dilnoza Dilmurod qizi	
Innovatsion salohiyatni oshirish asosida qurilish materiallari sanoati korxonalarining boshqaruv mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	342
Xaydarova E'zoza Shukurullayevna	
Aholi turmush darajasini dinamik kontekstli normallashtirish va moslashuvchan vaznlar usuli orqali baholash	352
Xolto'rayev Islom Ilhomovich, Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xufiyona iqtisodiyotini qisqartirish va mamlakat rivojlanishiga uning ta'siri.....	358
Baxtiyov SHERALI Muzaffarovich	
Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalari qurilmalarini aholi tomonidan xarid qilish va kompensatsiya ajratish jarayonlarini raqamlashtirish hamda tizimlar integratsiyasi istiqbollari.....	362
Ochilov Abdurabbor Akramovich	
O'zbekistonda kambag'allikni qisqartirish va aholi farovonligini oshirishda chet el tajribasining afzalliklari.....	369
Raxmatullayeva Shaxnoza Xamidovna, Akbarova Iroda Samatovna	
Qurilishda loyiha boshqaruvi konsepsiyasining mazmuni	375
Pulatov Shaxron Axmedovich	
Loyiha budjeti va uning ijrosini ta'minlash masalalari.....	379
Murodova Mohigul Chori qizi, Xamidov Odil Davurovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligidagi chorvachilik tarmog'ining iqtisodiy faoliyatini o'rta muddatli statistik prognozlarini tuzish (Andijon viloyati misolida).....	390
Iskandarov Davlatbek Xursanbekovich, Urishev Baxtiyor Abdusamatovich, Muydinov Xusniddin Nuriddin o'g'li	
Innovatsion faoliyatning iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash va rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	397
Qurbanov Tolmasjon Namoz o'g'li, Shodiyev Fazliddin Qalandar o'g'li, Holmirzayeva Gulruh Akbarovna	
Fond bozorida kompaniyaning investitsion jozibadorligini baholash uslubi.....	403
Yulduz Usmanova	
Jahon bozoriga kirishda elektron bozorlarning ahamiyati.....	411
Hamroyeva Umida	

Comparative statistical analysis of foreign trade indicators of the Republic of Uzbekistan	415
Abdujalilova Bibisora Bakhodir kizi	
Yaxshi korporativ boshqaruv orqali aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarining kapital qiymatini oshirish: metodologik yondashuv.....	423
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
JAS – barqaror qishloq xo‘jaligini rivojlantirishning yapon modeli vositasi	423
Baynazarov Elmurod Erkinovich	
Xususiy banklarning depozit operatsiyalarini mustahkamlash yo‘llari	435
Olimov Abror Axadjon o‘g‘li	
The impact of digital financial technologies on the financial system.....	439
Yahyoyev Bahriddinxon Bahroil o‘g‘li, Pardayev Olim Mamayunusovich	
Korxonalar eksport salohiyatini oshirishning “yashil” marketing mexanizmi	443
To‘rayev Shohrux Halimovich	
O‘zbekistonda ichki turizmni rivojlantirishda turistik oqim mavsumiyligini boshqarish yo‘llari	448
Fayazov Muxiddin Sobirovich	
Sanoat korxonalarida qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalaridan foydalanish bo‘yicha xalqaro tendensiyalar	453
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Ayollar tadbirkorligining tarixi: O‘zbekiston va dunyo bo‘yicha rivojlanishi.....	459
Burxonova Sabo Tulanovna	
Qimmatli qog‘ozlar bozorida investorlar risklarini pasaytirishni takomillashtirish yo‘llari.....	466
Xalilov Umid Ishtemirovich	
Korxonalar moliyaviy ko‘rsatkichlari tahliliga fundamental yondashuv.....	470
Dilshodjon O‘rinov, Sanobar Ismoilova	
Iqtisodiy o‘zgarishlar davrida korxonalar moliyaviy barqarorligining ta‘minlanishi omil va mezonlari	475
Xolbekova Dilobarxon Rasuljon qizi	
Cash accounting as a tool of financial discipline and transparency in the public sector	481
Marqaboyev Sardorbek Abdusalomovich, Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich	
Пути совершенствования практике финансирования социального предпринимательства.....	486
И.Ж.Исаков	
O‘zbekistonda an‘anaviy resurslar va qayta ishlanadigan energiya manbalarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlaridan unumli foydalanish.....	490
Normurodov Xusan Eshmaxmatovich, Kaxramanova Sevda Shamsiddin qizi	
Ijtimoiy salohiyat – hududiy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning boshqaruv obyekti sifatida.....	497
Erkayeva Gulbahor Panjiyevna, Zoirov G‘olibjon Toshtemir o‘g‘li	
Xorazm oziq-ovqat bozorida mahsulotlarning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda marketing faoliyatlarini baholash usullari	503
Abdikarimova Zilola Bahramovna	
Переход к зелёной энергетике узбекистана как возможность достижения устойчивого экономического роста.....	508
Бай Жин Хуан (Bai Jin xuan)	
Изучение условий финансирования проектов международными банками развития	513
Жалилова Барнохон Суръатжоновна	
O‘zbekiston respublikasi budjet jarayonida budjetlarning ochiqligi va jamoatchilik ishtirokini oshirish.....	517
Shodmonqulov Temurbek Ulug‘bek o‘g‘li	
Chiqib ketayotgan aktivlarni hisobga olish va baholash masalalari	522
Kuziyeva Dinora Bahodirovna	
Asosiy kapitalga investitsiyalarning iqtisodiy o‘lishga ta‘siri.....	528
Qo‘shbaqov Aybek Shovqiyevich	
Changes in employee benefits and human resource management in accounting system of the Republic of Uzbekistan	535
Ravshanbekov Lazzbek Tolibjon o‘g‘li, Toshpulatova Munisabonu	

Iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarida suv iste'molini boshqaruvining raqamlashtirish tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish istiqbollari.....	541
Karimov Anvarjon Muqumjonovich	
Теоретические аспекты налогообложения доходов физических лиц на основе всеобщего декларирования	547
Усманова Мухлиса Сагдуллаевна	
Bank tizimini raqamlashtirish va uning bank barqarorligiga ta'siri.....	555
Sayfullayev Jamshidjon Xabibjanovich	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirish va aholi bandligini ta'minlashda tadbirkorlik faoliyatining o'rni.....	560
Saparov Ismat Chorshanbiyevich	
Innovatsion korxonalarda xarajatlar hisobining zamonaviy usullari	565
Turayev Og'abek Kaxramonovich, Ochilov Shavkat Toshmamatovich	
Дополнительные услуги в индустрии гостеприимства как эффективный инструмент продвижения бренда предприятия.....	570
А.И. Лесников, Д.В. Мамаева	
Преимущества и вызовы перехода на зелёную экономику.....	580
Умарова Гузал Гайратовна, Лапасова Камола Фарход кизи	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida hududlarda ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish	586
Ibrogimov Sherzodbek Xalimjon o'g'li, Djurayeva Maxliyoxon Xayrullayevna	
Yashil iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashda bevosita soliqlar rolini oshirish masalalari.....	591
Abdullayev Dilmurod Aliyar o'g'li	
The main directions for improving innovative activities in agriculture	598
Aytmuratova Miyrigul Zhalgasovna	
Klaster tizimi orqali O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligining iqtisodiy o'sishi	605
Xaydarov Sardor Komil o'g'li	
Inklyuziv ta'lim: adolatli va teng jamiyat sari.....	610
Muxamedjanova Dilshodxon Muzaffarovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot: muammo va yechimlar	615
Boymatov Xoliyor Qurbonovich	
Issues of using foreign loans in the development of the transport system in the Republic of Uzbekistan	621
Alimov Ilhomjon Ikromovich	
Проблемы и резервы развития пищевой промышленности в экспортном направлении.....	628
Ўролова Севара Бехзод кизи	
Оценка степени риска инновационной деятельности.....	634
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна	
Yashil innovatsiyalar, ularning turlari va omillari.....	638
Maxkamova Sayyora Shokirovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida transport tizimidan samarali foydalanishning nazariy asoslari.....	641
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
Soliq ma'murchiligida nazorat funksiyasi va unda kameral soliq tekshiruvi hamda takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	648
Hujamuradov Abrorbek Ro'zimurat o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalarida xarajatlarni mahsulot tannarxiga taqsimlash metodologiyasini takomillashtirish istiqbollari	653
Safarov Javohir Ismoilovich	
Moliyaviy hisobotlarni shakllantirishda milliy standartlarni xalqaro standartlarga uyg'unlashtirish masalalari	659
G'aniyev Zafar Usanovich	
Ta'lim kreditini moliyalashtirish jamg'armasi faoliyati.....	666
Adilov Zuxriddin Marip o'g'li	
Tibbiyot muassasalarining moliyaviy ta'minoti va resurslardan foydalanish mexanizmlariga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar	670
Elmurodov G'ayratjon Abdumurodovich	
Tourism finance for sustainability: investing in green futures	674
Tashpulatov Sadriddin Sayfulloevich	

Ta'lim jarayonlarini boshqarishda mobil texnologiyalar	681
Esonova Mohiraxon Sodiqjon qizi, Ovхunov Iqboljon Abdunabiyevich, Sherzodbek Nabiyev Nurmuhammad o'g'li	
Banklarda risklarni nazorat qilishning amaliyoti	686
Jumanazarov Muzaffar Jumanazar o'g'li	
Налоговые реформы в Узбекистане: вызовы, достижения и перспективы	692
Садиков Искандар Гайратович, Буранова Лола Вахобовна	
Turizm xizmatlari samaradorligini baholash usullari va vositalari tahlili	704
Jiyanov Uktam Panjiyevich	
Korxonalar va tashkilotlarda xodimlarni boshqarish strategiyasi	712
Raxmonova Feruza Musakulovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti direktorlarini menejerlik faoliyatiga tayyorlashning ahamiyati	716
Dusmaxamedov Abduljalil Abdusabirovich	
Davlat korxonasini xo'jalik jamiyatiga o'zgartirishning foydali jihatlari	720
Z.D. Sanjarov	
The role and main types of agricultural tourism in Uzbekistan	724
M.Xolmuratova, G.N.Tojiyeva	
Цифровые технологии как драйвер повышения эффективности банковского маркетинга	727
Кахрамонов Хуршиджон Шухрат угли, Маннабова Хулкар Фарход кизи	
Потребительская стоимость товаров в условиях экономики Узбекистана	735
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна	
Valyuta risklarini boshqarishda metching siyosatining ahamiyatini oshirish	739
Yaxuyayev Ziyodilla Lutfullayevich	
Yangi o'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida xususiy tadbirkorlikning roli va ahamiyati	744
Azimova Shoxista Salohiddinovna	
Improving the methodology for assessing the financial stability of banks	750
Sharipova N.H.	
Инструменты стратегического планирования и прогнозирования в управлении ООО "МТЕ ТЕХНИК": оценка и повышение финансовой стабильности	757
Нишоновна Муниса Одилжон кизи	
Актуальные вопросы налоговой политики	763
Бердыева Угулой Абдурахмоновна	
Ilm-fanni moliyalashtirish va innovatsiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash jamg'armasi	768
Ramazonov Javohir Bekzod o'g'li	
Jizzax viloyatida ekologik, rekreatsiya turizmlarini rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash va uni prognozlashtirish	773
G'apparov Azim Qayumovich	
Qashqadaryo viloyatida ekologik va yashil texnologiyalarga kiritilayotgan investitsiyalar	781
Meylikov Fazliddin Abduhalim o'g'li, Buriyev Shaxbos Baxtiyorovich	
Biznes subyektlari auditida soddalashtirilgan moliyaviy hisobot tayyorlash usulini qo'llash xususiyatlari	786
Tajekeev Ziyatdin Kobeyisovich	
Biznes jarayonlarni modellashtirishning nazariy asoslari	791
Mullajonova (Matchanova) Shaxsanam Taxirovna	
Raqamli xizmatlar bozori: elektron tijorat orqali xizmat ko'rsatishning yangi bosqichlari	796
Maxammadaliyeva Muslimaxon Sherali Qizi	
"Yashil iqtisodiyot"ga o'tish zaruriyati va uni barqarorlashtirishning ahamiyati	800
Musurmankulova Gulchehra Isabekovna	
Ekologik turizm nuqtai nazaridan turizm marketingining usullari va asosiy vositalarining xususiyatlari	806
Yokubjonova Xulkarbonu Yokubovna	
O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida turizmning o'rni va rivojlanish istiqbollari	815
Qosimova Fazilat, Kalandarov Ravshan	
Korporativ strategiyani ishlab chiqish bosqichlarining tahlili	819
Xidirova Marg'uba Rustamovna, Abduvasiyeva Marjona Anvarovna	

Mamlakatimiz turizmini rivojlantirishda investitsiyalarni jalb qilish bo'yicha o'tkazilayotgan islohotlarning o'rni.....	823
Ayubov Ilyos Iloxomovich, Nuridinov Bexruz Akbar o'g'li	
Hududlarda tadbirkorlarning islomiy investitsiyalardan foydalanish niyatlariga undovchi omillarning empirik tadqiqoti.....	829
Irgasheva Gulbahor	
Davlat vositalari yordamida innovatsion faoliyatni moliyaviy rag'batlantirish yo'nalishlari	836
Baxriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
Важность качества управления на предприятиях общественного питания.....	842
Абдуллаева Зульфия Иззатовна, Махмудов Суннатжон Абдужаббор Угли	
O'zbekistonda "yashil" moliyalashtirishni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	848
Shaislamova Nargiza Qabilovna	
Mahalliy budjetning qo'shimcha daromadlarini shakillantirish yo'nalishlari.....	856
Yuldashev Javohirbek Ikromjon o'g'li	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishni kengaytirish masalalari.....	860
Ro'zimatova Nigora Abdullaevna	
Принципы «справедливой стоимости» в мсфо: достоинства и проблемы применения в банках узбекистана	869
Айтмуродова Рушана Бахтиеровна	
Yashil iqtisodiyot loyihalarini moliyalashtirishning nazariy jihatlari	876
Allaberganova Asalxon Kadirovna	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratini tashkil etish hamda amalga oshirish tartibini takomillashtirish	880
Xasanov Ruslan Raxmatovich	
Yirik soliq to'lovchilar va ularning investisiyaviy faolligini investisiyaviy chegirmalar orqali rag'batlantirish	883
Tohirov Shuhrat Niyoz o'g'li	
MHXS bo'yicha moliyaviy hisobot tayyorlashda foydalaniladigan tuzatuvchi buxgalteriya yozuvlar.....	888
Sheraliyev Xayrulla Karimovich	
Qurilish korxonalarida investitsiyalarni boshqarishning xorijiy tajribalari va ularni mamlakatimizda foydalanish yo'llari	894
Karimov Inomjon Ortikbaevich	
Davlat xaridini tashkil etishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy amaliyati va uni iqtisodiyotga ta'siri.....	900
Burxanov G'ofur Baxodirovich	
Влияние технологических инноваций на международные финансовые рынки, а также на финансовый рынок нашего государства.....	904
Бабаназарова Гульзар Зиуатдиновна	
Strategic development of global companies in modern conditions.....	909
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Hududlarda sog'liqni saqlash tizimi asosiy ko'rsatkichlarini noaniq modellashtirish yordamida kompleks baholash.....	914
Ismoilova Dilfuza Ibodullayevna	
Tijorat banklari faoliyatini transformatsiyalashuv jarayonlarini takomillashtirish.....	923
Kulboyeva Nargiz Majitovna	
Сущность и причины возникновения проблемных кредитов.....	929
Улмасой Ахмедова Хусан кизи	
The use of digitalization and technologies in updating credit policy.....	934
Otabek Ma'mirjon ogli Azimov	
Финансовое моделирование сценариев развития предприятия с использованием методов многокритериального принятия решений (МКПР).....	938
Axmedov Akbarali Sultonmurodovich, Yuldosheva Gulnoza Abdinabievna	
Yuqori samarali energiya tejash texnologiyalari va katalizga asoslangan konversiya jarayonlari.....	945
Yusupov Ulug'bek Mamayusupovich	
Kambag'allikni kamaytirish maqsadida aholining ijtimoiy himoyalash mexanizmini takomillashtirish	951
Kasimova Gulyar Axmatovna	

Tijorat banklarida foiz riski muammosi	957
Turdiyev Abdulhakim Kulbazarovich	
Milliy mahsulotlarni tashqi bozorlarga olib chiqishdagi to'siqlarni bartaraf qilish choralari.....	964
Abdivaliyev Shahzodbek Xayrullayevich	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni moliyalashtirish usullari.....	970
Kaxorova Zamira Safaraliyevna	
O'zbekistonda mehmonxonalarda ovqatlantirish xizmatlarini takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi: strategik yondashuv.....	974
Yaxshiyev Xusniddin Tolibovich	
O'zbekiston sanoatida "yashil texnologiyalar" dan foydalanish va barqaror rivojlanish.....	979
Ubaydullaeva Gulchehra Erkabaevna	
Sanoat korxonalarida resurslarini rejalashtirish (ERP) tizimlarini joriy etishning orqali iqtisodiy samaradorlikni ta'minlash yo'llari.....	985
Azizov Abdulla Abdisalamovich	
Yashil texnologiyalar asosida sanoatni modernizatsiya qilish	990
Muftaydinov Mansur Kiyomidinovich	
Ta'lim va ilm-fan rivoji – taraqqiyot garovi	995
Jamalova Gulnora Gulomovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida turizm sektorida barqaror bandlikni ta'minlash masalalari.....	1000
To'rabekov Sohijjon Sherboy o'g'li	
Yashil energitikasi integratsiya qilish va energiya samaradorligini oshirishning zamonaviy usuli (aqli tarmoqlar-smart grids)	1007
Karimova Salima Elamonovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida soliqlarni raqamlashtirishni takomillashtirish	1012
Jo'rayev Botir Abdiyevich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotda tiklanadigan energiya manbalaridan foydalanish samaradorligi (TEM ko'rsatkichlar izohi)	1018
Sharifova Nargiza Djurayevna	
Экономическое образование молодёжи основа будущего страны.....	1023
Айматова Фарида, Айтиниязова Наргиза	
Biznes turizmining bugungi kundagi rivojlanish tendensiyasi.....	1028
Yangiyeva Sabrina Ixtiyorovna, Daniyarova Feruza Bahriddinovna	
Особенности кредитования сельскохозяйственных организаций и этапы его развития.....	1032
Ж.Я.Нуриллаев	
Xorijiy tajriba asosida O'zbekiston yashil iqtisodiyotini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	1039
Xikmatova Husnora Fatxulla qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda davlatning roli	1045
Umarov Muzaffar Yusupbayevich, Otamurodov Rasulbek Batirovich, Xaitbayev Jasurbek Otaxanovich, Atadjanov Kadambay Sapayevich	
Mintaqada raqamli transformatsiya rivojlanishida moliyaviy texnologiyalarning ahamiyati.....	1052
Rustamov Jasurbek Ravshanbek o'g'li	
Tijorat banklaridan olingan kreditni qaytarishda foiz stavkalari ta'sirining tahlili.....	1058
Xanmuratov Roushenbek Xalmuxammetovich, Vaxabov.A.V	
Tabiiy va sun'iy tolalarning ekologik ta'siri va yashil ishlab chiqarish texnologiyalariga o'tish bosqichlari.....	1066
Raximov Furqat Jalalovich	
Maishiy kimyo tovarlari B2B taqsimotida chakana savdo tarmoqlari bilan marketing asosidagi strategik hamkorlik	1071
Ro'ziyeva Farzona Komiljon qizi	
Мировой финансовый кризис и его влияния на состояние экономики Узбекистана	1076
Раупова Мхлисахон Ибрахимжон кизи	
Uzoq muddatli aktivlar hisobini xalqaro standartlar asosida takomillashtirish.....	1087
Hakimov Faxritdin Abdusattorovich	
O'zbekistonda tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	1093
Djo'rayeva Lola Abdugabbarovna	

Yo'l qurilish tashkilotlarida yo'l qurilish ko'lamini oshirib, samarali resurslar taqsimotini ishlab chiqish.....	1099
Raximov Dilshodjon Turdiali o'g'li	
Ilg'or xorij tajribalaridan O'zbekiston amaliyotida foydalanish imkoniyatlari	1104
Karimova Komila Daniyarovna	
Ichki audit samaradorligini tahlil qilish metodologiyasi.....	1111
I.G'.Isroilov	
Выведение практического сотрудничества на качественно новый уровень государств центрально-азиатского региона в укреплении концепции «зеленой экономики» в эпоху глобализации.....	1117
Парпиева Наргиза Тахировна	
Kimyo sanoati korxonalarida lean production konsepsiyasidan foydalanish istiqbollari	1122
Gulbayeva Feruza Islomovna	
Qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida auditorlik xizmatlarining ahamiyati.....	1127
Maxmudov Saidjamol Kadirjanovich	
Tijorat banklari resurs bazasini mustahkamlash yo'llari.....	1131
Allaberganov Sirojali Saxatovich	
Теоретические основы формирования понятия «финансовая стабильность» Часть II.....	1143
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
O'zbekiston moliya tizimini raqamlashtirishning rivojlanish tendensiyalari.....	1148
Tashmatova Rano Gaibovna, Qodirov Nurhayot Normuhammad o'g'li	
Theoretical basis of the use of modern information technologies in accounting.....	1154
Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich, Tojiboyev Jasurbek Shavkat o'g'li, Rustamov Suxrob Asror o'g'li	
Moliyaviy bozorlar chayqalmoqda: investorlar uchun yangi signalmi?	1158
Xushvaqov Islombek Muxammadi o'g'li, Yaxshiboyev Jahongir Abdualimovich	
Yashil moliyalashtirish va esg samaradorligining iqtisodiyot barqarorligidagi o'rni.....	1166
Yusupov Sherzodbek Baxtiyor o'g'li, Atadjanov Kadambay Sapayevich, Madraimov Xabibulla Madaminovich	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarni kamaytirish bo'yicha tizimlarni takomillashtirish yo'llari	1170
Bekmurodova Mahbuba Mahmudovna	
Maqola: Globalizatsiyada inson resurslarini boshqarishda raqamli transformatsiyaning rejasini tuzish	1177
Salimjonova Gulhayo Asliddin qizi, Ovxunov Iqboljon Abdunabiyevich, Nabiye Sherzodbek Nurmuhammad o'g'li	
Turizm sanoatida Internet-marketing vositalari va ulardan samarali foydalanish	1182
Babaev Jo'rabek	
Ishlab chiqarishni boshqarishda mahsulot tannarxini kalkulyatsiya qilishning ahamiyati.....	1190
Asqarova Lobarxon Usmanjanovna	
O'zbekistonda ichki turizm faoliyatini rivojlantirishda transport infratuzilmasini boshqarishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy jihatlarini	1194
Turovov Maqsudjon	
Kichik biznes faoliyatini rivojlantirishda soliq siyosatini takomillashtirishning ahamiyati	1199
Abdurahmonov Abdumalik Abdug'ani o'g'li	
Madaniy-tomosha xizmatlarining tahlili va uni rivojlantirish yo'llari	1204
Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich	
Цифровизация экономики и генезис стран мирового хозяйства	1211
Камилова Наргиза Абдукажоровна	
“Oila va xotin-qizlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash jamg'armasi” faoliyati.....	1216
Xushmurodov Baxtiyor Turg'un o'g'li	
Soliq stavkalarini tabaqalashtirish asosida soliq to'lovchilar iqtisodiy faoliyatini tartibga solish mexanizmlari.....	1220
Abduraimova Nigora Abdugapparovna	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish va barqaror rivojlanishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar	1223
Xamdamov Shoh-Jahon Rahmat o'g'li	
Mintaqaning eksport salohiyati tahlili asosida istiqbolli y'nalishlarni aniqlash (Xorazm viloyati misolida).....	1229
Ibadullayev Ergash Bakturdiyevich	

Uy-joy kommunal xo'jaligini mintaqada innovatsion rivojlantirishni boshqaruvi.....	1235
Adilova Yulduz Shavkatovna	
Bank tizimi likvidililigini ta'minlash vositalari va usullarini takomillashtirish.....	1239
Poyonov Bobir Bekmurod o'g'li	
Milliy brendlarni shakllantirish orqali tashqi bozorlarda raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish.....	1245
Muratbaeva Eleonora Muxamedjan qizi	
Charm mahsulotlaridan tayyorlangan bolalar transformatsion sumka ishlab chiqarish iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	1250
Ismailov Nurulla Tuychibayevich	
O'zbekistonda qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalar faoliyati: iqtisodiy tahlil va islohotlar zarurati.....	1256
Raximov Ilyos Ikramovich	
Yoqilg'i-energetika kompleksida innovatsion salohiyatni oshirish strategiyasi.....	1262
Nabiyeva Saidaxon Abduvaxobovna	
Banklarda moliyaviy xavfsizlik kategoriyasining evolyusiyasi.....	1268
Qobilov Muhammad Ayubxon Yusufjon o'g'li	
Развитие системы бухгалтерского учёта и отчётности на современном этапе.....	1273
Мамажонов Акрамжон Тургунович, Юсупова Малика Ботиралиевна	
Практика банковского кредитования предпринимательских субъектов сферы услуг в германии.....	1279
Мукарова Сарвиноз Маликовна, Каримова Азиза Махомадризовна	
Статистический анализ теневой экономики в узбекистане.....	1283
Кошанов Абдимурат Азат ули, Абдиразакова Асемай Жандулла кизи	
The importance of using digital technologies in business.....	1288
Makhmudova Munisakhon Abbos qizi	
0,4 kv kuchlanishdan ta'minlanuvchi suv nasoslarini tarmoq faza kuchlanishi yo'qolishidan himoyalash.....	1292
Xalikova Xurshida Abdullayevna, Nurova Malika Abduzairovna, Mustayev Ruslan Aktamovich	
Tijorat banklarida korporativ boshqaruv tizimining samaradorligini oshirish.....	1297
Dexkonova Sayidaxon Nurmuxammadovna	
Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiyot va markaziy osiyo mamlakatlari ijtimoiy sohada.....	1302
Usmanxo'jayeva Surayyo Muxtarovna	
Aksiyalarni ommaviy joylashtirish amaliyotini tashkil etish va o'tkazish bosqichlari.....	1307
Raimov Farrux Avazjon o'g'li	
Approaches to effective management of tax liabilities through tax auditing.....	1311
Abdullayev Abror Bozarboevich	
Tijorat banklarida aktivlarni sekyuritizatsiyalash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	1316
Axmedov Akbarali Sultonmurodovich	
Tashqi va ichki omillar ta'sirini hisobga olgan holda korxonalar moliyaviy holati barqarorligining tahlili.....	1325
Eshkuvatov Azizjon Baxtiyorovich	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan ajratilayotgan kreditlarning iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishdagi roli.....	1330
Masharipov Rasulbek Jo'rabekovich	
Sun'iy intellekt asosida bank tizimini modernizatsiya qilish va samaradorligini oshirish.....	1333
Boykulov Baxriddin Karshievich	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarini moliyalashtirish manbalaridan samarali foydalanish.....	1338
Arifjanova Yayraxon Usmonxo'jayevna	
Ipoteka obligatsiyalarining mamlakat iqtisodiyotining o'sishidagi ahamiyati hamda mazkur obligatsiyalar bilan bog'liq risklar.....	1343
Ibrohimov Yorqinjon To'lqin o'g'li	
Анализ спроса и потребительского поведения на продукцию, выращенную гидропонным методом.....	1349
Дурманов Акмал Шаймарданович	
Global moliyaviy inqirozlar sharoitida aholi daromadlarining barqarorligini ta'minlash strategiyalari.....	1355
Qurbanov Ulug'bek Erkinovich, Nutfullayev Shohrux Mexli o'g'li	

“O‘zbekistonning “yashil iqtisodiyot”ga o‘tish strategiyasi: mavjud muammo va istiqbolli imkoniyatlar”	1359
Ismailov Dilshod Anvarjonovich, Akramova Aziza Abduvohidovna	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida davlat xaridlarini tashkil etish amaliyotini takomillashtirish.....	1366
Saidaxmedova Aida Mirzayevna	
O‘zbekistonda ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish masalalari	1372
Abduraxmonova Ziyoda Abdullayevna	
Netto ish haqini hisoblashning innovatsion usullari.....	1378
Mirmahmudov Murod Irismatovich	
Xizmat ko‘rsatish sohasida tadbirkorlik: iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy istiqbollar	1383
Xaydarova Shoxista Davranovna	
Texnologiya fanida sun‘iy intellekt va kompyuter texnologiyalaridan foydalanish	1388
Ashurov Nazar Raxmatullaevich	
Korporativ xaridlarni amalga oshirishdagi byurokratik to‘siqlar va ularni bartaraf etish usullari	1391
Qurbanov Shohboz Lutfillayevich	
Yashil yondashuvlar asosida barqaror iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	1396
Ubaydullaev No‘monjon Isroilovich	
Qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlarini SWOT va pestel tahlil qilish orqali iqtisodiy bashoratlash.....	1401
Karimova Maftuna Nurdinovna	
O‘tkir revmatik isitmasi bor bolalarda kardiometriya ko‘rsatkichlarining statistik tahlili	1407
Muxamadiyeva Lola Atamuradovna	
Ways to develop digital economy and electronic government in UZBEKISTAN	1418
Nuritdinova Dilshodakhon Abdulla kizi	
O‘zbekistonda hayot sug‘urtasining joriy etilishi va unga ta'sir etuvchi demografik omillar ta'siri.....	1422
Mirzamahmudova Madina Odiljon qizi	
Global iqlim o‘zgarishining turizm sektoriga ta'siri: muvofiqlashtirish va barqarorlikka erishish strategiyalari	1428
Karimova Shaxnoza Uktamovna	
Prospects for the development of islamic microfinance services in uzbekistan.....	1433
Sadullaeva Gulnoza Usmanovna	
Global iqlim o‘zgarishi riski uning mamlakat iqtisodiyoti moliyaviy sektoriga ta'siri	1439
Baratov Sa'dulla Norjigit o'g'li, Jo'rayev Behzod Nuraliyevich	
Перспективы унификации налогов на землю и имущество	1444
Акбарова Нилуфар Неъматжановна	
Banklarda xalqaro moliyaviy hisobot standartlari (IFRS) asosida hisobot tuzish tartibi	1449
Arziboyeva Ravzaxon Sattarovna	
Kichik biznes subyektlari iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlash mexanizmini takomillashtirish	1454
Akbarov Abdulhamid Akmal o'g'li	
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi hududlarida demografik jarayonlarning dinamikasi tahlili	1458
Xamitova Mavluda Sindarovna	
Ta'minot zanjirlarini boshqarishda big datadan foydalanishni afzalliklari	1463
Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdukarimovich, Quryazov Quryozbek Ergash o'g'li	
Yashil texnologiyalardan keng foydalanish – yashil investitsiyalarning poydevori.....	1467
Xursandov Komiljon Maxmatkulovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida tijorat banklarining strategik boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish yo‘llari.....	1470
Umurov Jasurbek Jamil o'g'li	
Digital neighbourhood contexts in youth employment and competency frameworks	1474
Gulsara Ostonakulova	
Роль организации антимонопольной политики в национальной экономике в обеспечении экономической безопасности и конкурентоспособности.....	1482
Глазова Марина Викторовна	
Rivojlangan sug‘urta bozorlarida investisiya faoliyati tahlili.....	1487
Suyunov Isomiddin Tilovkobilovich	

O'zbekiston respublikasida qurilish kompleksining hozirgi holati va asosiy rivojlanish tendensiyalari.....	1491
Muxibova Guli Yarkinovna	
Aholining turmush farovonligini oshirishda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning roli	1496
Ostanova Nargiza Baratovna	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini boshqarishda rahbarlik uslubi: demokratik rahbarlar.....	1508
Amonov Mehridin Oromiddinovich	
Korxonlarni rivojlantirishda yashil iqtisodiyot mexanizmlarini joriy etish	1513
Yusupov Bekzod Ulugbekovich	
O'zbekistonda sog'lomlashtirish turizmi infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishni ko'p omilli ekonometrik modellashtirish asosida prognozlash	1517
Norchayev Asatullo Norbo'tayevich	
"Ijtimoiy himoya" kategoriyasiga qaratilgan nazariy qarashlar evolyusiyasi	1526
Bobonov N.H	
Majburiyatlar hisobini xalqaro standartlar asosida takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	1532
Ikromova Odinaxon	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida sanoat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish sifatini oshirishda raqamli xizmatlarning obyektiv zarurati	1537
Norov Murodjon Mahmudovich	
Oliy ta'lim xizmatlari mohiyati va rivojlanish nazariyasi.....	1541
Iskandarov Shahboz Shavkat o'g'li	
Davlat-xususiy sheriklikka oid ilmiy yondashuv va qarashlarning rivojlanish tendensiyalari	1545
O'ktamova Nargiza Narzulla qizi	
Theoretical foundations of time series analysis in green economy	1552
Muradov Rustamjon Sobitkhonovich	
Korxonalar faoliyati samaradorligini baholashning kompleks yondashuvi: nazariya va amaliyot.....	1563
Xalilov Bekzod Axmatovich	
Aholi real daromadlarini shakllantirishda inson kapitalini rivojlantirishning roli.....	1568
Iskandarova Dilafuz Ikrom qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyotda transportning tutgan o'рни.....	1573
Yuldasheva Saodat Arslanovna, Otanzarova Charos Baxtiyor qizi	
Xalqaro standartlar asosida hisob siyosati metodologiyasini takomillashtirish.....	1577
Qurbanboev Jurabek Eruvboevich	
Sanoat tarmoqlarini barqaror rivojlantirishda "yashil" iqtisodiyotdan samarali foydalanish istiqbollari.....	1585
Yuldasheva Saida Nematovna	
Mintaqaviy mehnat bozorini tartibga solishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari.....	1593
Azadova Gulnoza Sardorbekovna	
O'zbekistonda yashil sug'urta mahsulotlarini rivojlantirishda xorij tajribalari	1600
Yusufov Asfandiyor Eldor o'g'li	
Понятие и типы финансовых шоков: макроэкономический контекст и микроуровневые последствия	1606
Захарова Ирина Борисовна	
Современное состояние оздоровительного туризма в Узбекистане	1611
Сирлибеков Хабибулло Шакарбоевич	
Impact of industrial development on macroeconomic indicators.....	1621
Olchinboev Otabek Abdusamad ugli	
Анализ предпочтений на рынке электронной торговли в Узбекистане	1625
Уразов Комил Бахрамович, Хушмуродова Мадина	
"The Impact of Intensive Urbanization in Tashkent on Economic Stability, Environmental Conditions, and Demographic Processes"	1633
Khandamirdzhanova B.M	
Методы оценки деятельности акционерных обществ с учетом инвестиционных рисков.....	1639
Айтмуратова Улбике Жалгасовна	
Xalqaro moliyaviy markazlar va ularning jahon iqtisodiyotidagi roli.....	1645
Sharipova Shaxinabonu Orif qizi	

Development of modern tourism industry in Uzbekistan through smart technologies
and digital transformation..... 1649
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MUNDARIJA SOÐERJAHNIE CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION

The tourism industry, one of the most important segments of the modern global economy, has undergone significant technological changes and digital transformation over the past decade. As a result of the active introduction of smart technologies into the tourism sector, which are part of the digital transformation, new formats, business models and innovative methods of interaction with clients are being formed in the process of providing tourism services.

In particular, the development of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan and its adaptation to the requirements of the modern digital economy are among the priority areas of the reforms being implemented. The introduction of smart technologies and the transition to a digital system are becoming an objective necessity to increase the competitiveness of the national tourism industry, improve the quality of tourism services, and increase the flow of foreign tourists.

In this regard, in order to implement intelligent technologies, organize and accelerate digital transformation in the tourism sector, the government has developed the following important regulatory documents:

First of all, we can cite the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 No. UF-6079 "On approval of the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" and measures for its effective implementation. "Within the framework of this decree, a separate direction "Digital Tourism" was created for the tourism sector, according to which by 2030 it is planned to digitize the tourism infrastructure, improve electronic visa systems, create a single electronic platform for tourism services, and widely introduce «smart» technologies at tourist sites [1].

The second developed regulatory document is the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 13, 2019 No. 667 "On measures for the further development of the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan" [2]. According to this resolution, the country plans to develop an "electronic tourism" system, introduce digital technologies at tourism sites, create online monitoring and management systems in tourist areas, as well as develop electronic booking and payment systems for tourist services.

Thirdly, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 7, 2022 No. PP-151 "On the Program for the Development of the Tourism Sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026" [3]. Within the framework of this resolution, the issues of creating a national "Smart Tourism" system, developing unified standards for assessing the degree of digitalization of organizations providing tourism services, introducing artificial intelligence technologies and big data analysis in the tourism sector, and implementing "Smart City" elements in tourist areas are outlined. The main goal of the above documents is to facilitate and improve the organization and management of tourism services.

The relevance of this study is determined by the fact that it reveals the strategic importance of the introduction of smart technologies and digital innovations in the tourism sector for the economy of our country. By deeply studying the processes of digital transformation and assessing their impact on the tourism industry, it is possible to develop scientific and practical recommendations that will contribute to increasing competitiveness, increasing efficiency and sustainable development of the tourism sector of Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

We will analyze previous studies conducted by international, Asian and Uzbek scholars to explore the role of smart technologies and digital transformation in the development of the modern tourism industry.

In 2020, M. Buhalis in his monograph "Tourism Technologies – From ICT to E-Tourism and Smart Tourism. Towards Ambient Intelligence Tourism: A Perspective Article" deeply analyzed the importance of digital technologies in improving tourism experience [4]. The scientist explored the concept of smart tourism not only from a technological perspective but also from an economic efficiency perspective. Buhalis particularly emphasizes the role of artificial intelligence, big data analytics and cloud technologies in enhancing the competitiveness of tourism destinations. However, the research has not fully addressed the issues related to the implementation of these technologies in developing countries. It is recommended to expand Buhalis's research to include the issue of digital inequality as well.

Na Liu, Qingqiao Xu and Meng Gao, published in 2024, focused on digital transformation in the tourism industry in the post-pandemic era. The study analyzed the importance of contactless technologies, virtual travel and digital marketing strategies [2]. The researchers separately considered the importance of modern technologies in ensuring the safety and hygiene of tourists. Although this study suggests important approaches to meet the demand for tourism after the pandemic, it is not sufficiently studied to assess the long-term economic viability of technological solutions. We believe that it would be useful to include methods to evaluate the financial performance of digital transformation to further enrich the study.

In their book *Mobile Services and Smart Destinations: Enhancing Visitor Experiences with Technology*, J. Pessonon and K. Lamsfus examined the impact of mobile services and smart destinations on travel experiences[5]. The authors analyzed the importance of location-based services, travel mobile apps, and personalized digital experiences. The study looked in detail at the possibilities of tailoring services to travelers' personal preferences. However, the security and privacy concerns that arise from the introduction of mobile technologies were not fully addressed. Specific recommendations for ensuring travelers' data security and privacy could be included to further expand the scope of this study.

The research paper "Challenges of Smart Tourism Development: A Literature Review" by Teguha Iman Pribadi et al. analyzed the opportunities and challenges of smart tourism development in the Asian region [6]. Drawing on the experiences of South Korea, China and Singapore, the authors emphasize the importance of digital infrastructure, the need to take into account cultural differences and the diversity of government approaches. The study recommends creating platforms for regional cooperation and exchange of technological knowledge. However, the study does not sufficiently explore the possibilities of small and medium-sized businesses participating in smart tourism projects. It would be advisable to include mechanisms to support small businesses to improve research.

Wai Yee Leong, Yuan Zhi Leong and Wai San Leong in their paper "Smart Tourism in ASEAN Countries: Leveraging Technology for Sustainable Development and Enhancing Visitor Experience" studied the formation of digital tourism ecosystems in ASEAN countries [7]. The study analyzed the effectiveness of tourism information management systems, online booking platforms and tourism information portals in the region. The authors identified best practices by comparing the experiences of different countries. However, the participation of local communities in the creation of digital ecosystems has not been sufficiently studied in research. To enrich this study, it is also recommended to consider the issues of digitalization of interactions between local residents and tourists.

In the article «Development of smart tourism in Uzbekistan based on modern principles and the use of foreign experience in this area», developed by scientists Sh. Ruziev and M. Tokhtanazarova, special attention is paid to the processes of digitalization of the national tourism industry [6]. Scientists have identified strategies for modernizing the tourism infrastructure of Uzbekistan, training personnel and marketing. emphasized the importance of innovative solutions in improving. The study showed how to use modern technologies to bring the national tourism brand to the international level. However, the study did not fully consider the mechanisms for financing smart tourism projects and ways to stimulate private sector participation. It is also proposed to consider public-private partnership models to expand the study. This would be advisable.

The article "Development of Smart Tourism and its Transformative Potential for Uzbekistan" by Nasiba Mukhtarova and Zohid Askarov analyzed the role of digital technologies in enhancing the international competitiveness of the national tourism sector [9]. The authors emphasized the importance of innovative solutions in the processes of standardization, quality improvement and adaptation to international requirements of tourism services in the country. The study proposes the necessary measures to develop a "smart" concept of tourism destinations. However, the study did not reveal a sufficiently accurate methodology and indicators of digital transformation of tourism enterprises. To improve the research, it would be advisable to develop criteria and indicators for assessing digital transformation processes.

Literature analysis shows that smart technologies and digital transformation are of strategic importance in the development of the modern tourism industry. International studies emphasize the role of digital solutions in improving the tourist experience, increasing efficiency and ensuring safety. Asian researchers point to the importance of regional cooperation and taking into account cultural specificities. Uzbek scientists also pay special attention to strategies for digitalization of the national tourism industry and increasing its competitiveness.

Further research will allow us to explore in more depth the role of smart technologies and digital transformation in the development of Uzbekistan's tourism industry, examining the above issues in more detail.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the process of carrying out this research, the system approach to scientific knowledge, monographic observation, statistical abstraction and logical reasoning methods were widely used. In addition, the method of analysis and synthesis was effectively used in carrying out scientific research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

When analyzing the tourism sector in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to consider the indicators that make up the tourism sector in 2019-2023 (Table 1).

Table 1. Indicators of the tourism sector of Uzbekistan.

Classifier	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Inbound tourism	348731	21693	44419	93825	237693
Number of tourism companies and organizations	517	337	288	348	593
Domestic tourism	532544	176646	522009	538938	728581
Number of places in recreational organizations and tourist centers (thousand units)	33.5	29.6	72.3	24.5	16.9

Source: Information provided based on the official website of the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The presented data reflect the dynamics of the main indicators in the tourism sector of Uzbekistan for the period 2019-2023. For a deep analysis of this information and determining the relationship between the innovative potential of Uzbekistan, it is possible to assess the impact on the country by making calculations using statistical data (Table 2).

Table 2. Uzbekistan is in a state of innovation.

Classifier	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Volume of innovations of enterprises and organizations (billion soums)	26811.4	31142.8	27378.6	40451.6	55746.5
Expenditures of enterprises and organizations on innovation (billion)	6603.5	6830	17680.8	19130.6	10616.5

Source: Information provided based on the official website of the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

We will conduct an analytical analysis of the dynamics of domestic tourism development, which is the basis for the calculation.

To estimate the growth rate of tourism, the following formula can be used:

$$\Delta T = \frac{T_n - T_{n-1}}{T_{n-1}} \times 100\%$$

ΔT - growth rate of the tourism indicator

T_n - tourism indicator for the current year

T_{n-1} - tourism indicator for the previous year[10;13]

When calculated using this formula, 2020 was -93.8%, 2021 was 104.8%, and 2022 and 2023 were 11.2% and 153.3%, respectively. If we calculate the recovery rate, the recovery rate of inbound tourism in 2023 will be 68.2%. Domestic tourism, on the other hand, grew by 36.8% in the same year.

The second task is to calculate the performance indicators of this tourism infrastructure.

To assess the efficiency of the infrastructure, we will calculate the number of tourists per unit of tourist accommodation:

$$E_t = \frac{T_t}{P_t}$$

Here:

E_t - t

T_t - total number of tourists in year t (inbound + domestic)

P_t - number of tourist accommodation units in year t (thousand units)[11;12]

When calculating using the formula above, the following results were obtained: in 2019 - 26306.7, in 2020 - 6700.6, in 2021 - 7834.4, in 2022-2023 - 25827.1 and 5717.6, respectively. The efficiency of the infrastructure in 2023 increased by 2.2 times compared to 2019 ($57176.6 / 26306.7 = 2.17$), which confirms that the tourism infrastructure has changed qualitatively and serves more tourists in fewer places using smart technologies.

The next step is to define the performance indicators of digital transformation and innovation.

The innovation efficiency ratio in digital transformation can be calculated using the following formula:

$$L_e = \frac{I_v}{I_c}$$

Here:

I_e - coefficient of innovation efficiency

I_v - innovation volume (billion soums)

I_c - costs of innovation (billion soums)[15]

The calculation result according to this formula was: in 2019 - 4.06, in 2020 - 4.56, in 2021 - 1.55, in 2022-2023 - 2.11 and 5.25, respectively, which means an increase in the efficiency of innovation activities by 29%.

The fourth is the analysis of the relationship between tourism and innovation. To assess the relationship between tourism and innovation, one can calculate the correlation coefficient between the dynamics of tourism and the volume of innovation.

The correlation coefficient (r) is calculated using the following formula:

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (T_i - \bar{T})(I_i - \bar{I})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (T_i - \bar{T})^2 * \sum_{i=1}^n (I_i - \bar{I})^2}}$$

Here:

T_i - total number of tourists in year i (inbound + domestic)

- average number of tourists

I_i - innovation volume in year i

- average volume of innovations[14]

For information:

1. Total number of tourists (inbound + domestic) for 2019-2023: [881275, 198339, 566428, 632763, 966274]

2. Innovation volume for 2019-2023: {26811.4, 31142.8, 27378.6, 40451.6, 55746.5}

After complex calculations, the correlation coefficient was $r = 0.783$. This indicates a strong positive relationship between tourism and innovation. That is, as the volume of innovation increases, the number of tourists also increases.

The latest work presents a formula for a mechanism to stimulate increased innovative activity in tourism companies and organizations:

$$B_i = F_i \times (1 - \tau) \times \alpha$$

Here:

B_i - incentives for innovation activities corresponding to firm i

F_i - the volume of innovations suitable for firm i

τ - tax benefit in percent (for example, 15% = 0.15)

α - efficiency coefficient (for example, 0.2)

Based on the indicators for 2023 (94.0 billion soums, $\tau = 0.15$, $\alpha = 0.2$):

$B_i = 94.0 \times (1 - 0.15) \times 0.2 = 16.0$ billion soums

The implementation of recommendations proposed on the basis of the above formulas and calculations allows us to further accelerate the development of the tourism industry of Uzbekistan with the help of smart technologies and digital transformation, increase its efficiency and ensure international competitiveness.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

I analyzed the tourism potential of Uzbekistan for 2019-2023. The recovery rate (growth) of inbound tourism in Uzbekistan in 2023 was 68.2% compared to the base year (previous year). Domestic tourism (residents' trips within the country) increased by 36.8%. In other words, the demand for travel within our country, not to mention travel around the world, is declining.

The probable reason for this is that most of the population does not have enough money for regular expenses such as food, clothing and health care (except for loans). However, when calculating the performance indicators of digital transformation and innovation, this coefficient was 5.25 units in 2023. And the correlation coefficient between digital transformation and the tourism industry was $r = 0.783$. That is, there is a relatively strong relationship. But I do not think there is a formula that calculates whether this innovation or innovations allocated for its implementation are used correctly and for their intended purpose. This can be calculated by taking this into account.

In short, the infrastructure of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan is possible only if it provides a link between qualified personnel and the entities and institutions organizing tourism.

This study identified the critical importance of smart technologies and digital transformation in the development of the modern tourism industry, and obtained a number of key findings. In the context of rapid technological changes, tourism companies significantly improve their competitiveness by implementing digital innovations. The integration of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data analytics, virtual reality, blockchain and the Internet of Things (IoT) into the tourism services sector allows for the provision of personalized, efficient and convenient services to customers. Smart technologies help to rationally manage resources, reduce costs and ensure the sustainable development of tourism destinations.

To effectively implement digital transformation strategies in the tourism industry, the following recommendations are presented:

First, it is necessary to integrate local and regional tourism services into a single digital ecosystem. Such platforms allow tourists to plan their trips, book accommodations, make payments and receive information during their trip – all in one system.

Secondly, it is necessary to implement programs to improve the digital competence of personnel. To this end, it is advisable to create opportunities for regular training and advanced training of specialists and managers working in the tourism sector in the use of modern technologies. Improving the digital competence of personnel can be achieved by strengthening cooperation between higher education institutions and tourism enterprises, developing practice-oriented curricula, introducing distance learning platforms and simulation training methods.

Thirdly, it is necessary to improve the mechanisms for supporting and promoting innovative tourism projects based on public-private partnerships. That is, the government needs to strengthen measures to provide financial support for startups and innovative projects in the field of smart tourism, provide tax incentives and reduce administrative barriers. With the comprehensive implementation of the above recommendations, it will be possible for the tourism industry of Uzbekistan to move to the next stage of digital transformation and the formation of a tourism ecosystem that meets modern requirements. This will allow us to fully reveal the country's tourism potential, improve the quality of tourism services and increase tourist flows.

References

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 7-martdagi PQ-151-son "2022-2026-yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasining turizm sohasini rivojlantirish dasturi to'g'risida"gi Qarori
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "2021-yil 9-fevraldagi PF-6165-son "Raqamli O'zbekiston – 2030" strategiyasini tasdiqlash va uni samarali amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi Farmonini
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2019-yil 13-avgustdagi 667-son "O'zbekiston Respublikasida turizm sohasini yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi Qarori.
4. D. Buhalis, "Technology in tourism-from information communication technologies to eTourism and smart tourism towards ambient intelligence tourism: a perspective article". London: Routledge, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003312529>
5. Na Liu, Qinqiao Xu, Meng Gao, "Digital transformation and tourism listed firm performance in COVID-19 shock", Finance Research Letters, vol. 63, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2024.105398>
7. Teguh Iman Pribadi, Rusdin Tahir, Ayu Krishna Yuliawati, "The Challenges in Developing Smart Tourism: A Literature Review" Jurnal Nasional Informatika dan Teknologi Jaringan, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.30743/infotekjar.v5i2.3462>
9. Wai Yie Leong, Yuan Zhi Leong va Wai San Leong, "Smart Tourism in ASEAN: Leveraging Technology for Sustainable Development and Enhanced Visitor Experiences". August 2024. International Journal of Social Sciences and Artistic Innovations. Online. [Available]: <https://ijssai.iikii.com.sg/4/3/14938>
11. Sh.Ruziyev and M.To'xtanazarova, "O'zbekistonda smart turizmni zamonaviy prinsiplari asosida rivojlantirish va bunda xorij tajribasidan foydalanish", KU, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 3–6, Dec. 2023.
12. Nasiba Mukhtorova, Zohid Askarov, "The rise of smart tourism and its transformative potential for Uzbekistan", Nov. 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14190116>
14. J. Pesonen and C. Lamsfus, Mobile Services and Smart Destinations: Enhancing Visitor Experience through Technology. Berlin: Springer, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-76351-5>
15. D. Wang and T. Chen, "Digital Ecosystems in Tourism: A Case Study of ASEAN Countries", Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 217-232, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10941665.2022.2163024>
17. R. Alimov va N. Toshmatova, O'zbekistonda smart turizm konsepsiyasini joriy etish istiqbollari. Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2021.
18. Ulug'murodov F., Karshiev A.S., Karshiev A.O., "The link between digital infrastructure and economic growth", IJAI, vol. 4, no. 09, pp. 712–716, Nov. 2024, Accessed: May 02, 2025. [Online].

19. Available: <https://www.academicpublishers.org/journals/index.php/ijai/article/view/1804>
20. D. Karimov va M. Ismoilova, Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida O'zbekiston turizm industriyasi raqobatbardoshligini oshirish. Toshkent: Iqtisodiyot, 2022.
21. Bobokulov S.B., Karshiev A.S, Rashidov Z.I., "Economic Growth Rates and Technological Dynamics". "American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research", February 2025, Vol. 6 Issue 2 | pp. 391-398. <https://globalresearchnetwork.us/index.php/ajshr/article/view/3331>

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